

Corrective Actions As Mediating Factor on the Relationship Between Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads and School Operational Efficiency

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Abstract. This study, titled "Corrective Actions as a Mediating Factor on the Relationship Between Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads and School Operational Efficiency," investigates the pivotal role of corrective actions in strengthening the connection between the financial stewardship abilities of school heads and the operational efficiency of schools within the district. Recognizing that effective financial management is critical to the success of educational institutions, the research aims to determine whether the implementation of timely and strategic corrective actions can enhance school operations by addressing gaps and optimizing resource utilization. The study involves the participation of teachers who serve as key stakeholders in providing firsthand insights into existing management practices. Their contributions are essential in identifying best practices and areas for improvement. Ultimately, the findings of this research will inform more effective leadership strategies, promote a culture of shared accountability, and foster a more collaborative and efficient educational environment.

KEY WORDS

1. Corrective Actions 2. Mediating Factor 3. Financial Stewardship Skills

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1. Introduction

School operational inefficiency remains a pressing concern in many educational settings, affecting day-to-day management and resource allocation. When schools operate below expectations, students, teachers, and the broader community can experience negative impacts on academic quality and access to necessary support. Existing literature suggests that inadequate financial stewardship skills among school heads may hinder swift, effective decisions that keep operations running smoothly (Bhutoria and Aljabri, 2022). In this context, adopting corrective actions can offer a strategic approach to address inefficiencies and enhance overall performance.

Therefore, this study intends to examine how corrective actions mediate the relationship between the financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency, shedding light on potential avenues for policy and practice improvements. School operational inefficiency is a pervasive issue affecting educational institutions across various regions, each presenting unique challenges. In Brazil, Agassiti, de Oliveira Ribeiro, and Montemor (2022) examine the efficiency of elementary public schools, highlighting that inadequate financial management and resource allocation are primary contributors to operational inefficiencies.

Their study reveals that schools struggling with these aspects often face difficulties in maintaining consistent educational quality and achieving desired student outcomes. Consequently, the lack of efficient financial practices hampers the ability of schools to utilize resources optimally, leading to diminished operational performance. In Africa, Osumba Olingo and Sang (2019) explore the operational efficiency of public universities in Kenya, identifying management science tools as critical factors in enhancing financial stewardship and overall institutional performance. Their research indicates that the absence of robust management practices and effective financial controls leads to significant inefficiencies, undermining the universities' ability to deliver quality education. Additionally, Ani (2019) discusses the broader context of African solutions to African problems, emphasizing that traditional governance and administrative practices often fall short in addressing the nuanced challenges of operational inefficiency in educational settings. This gap underscores the need for tailored management strategies that can effectively mitigate inefficiencies and promote sustainable educational development (Ani, 2019). Turning to Asia, Edukasia (2022) investigates the performance of public elementary schools in Indonesia, identifying several factors that contribute to operational inefficiency, including inadequate infrastructure and limited access to educational resources. The study emphasizes that these deficiencies not only impede the delivery of quality education but also affect teacher morale and student engagement. Similarly, Jiang, Lee, and Rah (2020) assess the research efficiency of Chinese higher education institutions using data envelopment analysis, finding that poor financial management and lack of strategic planning significantly detract from institutional efficiency. Their findings suggest that without effective financial stewardship and operational strategies, schools and universities in Asia struggle to achieve optimal performance and meet educational objectives. In the Philippines, Condez (2024) applies data envelopment analysis to evaluate the technical efficiency of State Universities and Colleges (SUCs), uncovering that many institutions suffer from inefficient resource utilization and inadequate financial oversight. Navarro (2022) further highlights the challenges in school infrastructure, noting that insufficient investment in physical facilities and maintenance exacerbates operational inefficiencies, thereby hindering the overall educational experience. These studies collectively illustrate that in the Philippine context, operational inefficiency is closely linked to financial mismanagement and infrastructural inadequacies, which impede the ability of schools to deliver effective education and maintain sustainable operations. In the Visayas region, operational inefficiency has been linked to poor financial planning and limited administrative support. Ocan et al. (2023) emphasized that many schools in rural areas experience delays in infrastructure projects due to slow budget approvals and bureaucratic red tape. Additionally, there have been reports of financial misallocation, where funds meant for classroom improvements were redirected to other expenses with minimal impact on student learning (Duma et al., 2022). These inefficiencies not only slow down school development but also contribute to teacher dissatisfaction and lower student engagement. Addressing these issues requires better monitoring and accountability mechanisms to ensure that financial resources are properly utilized. The necessity for this study arises from observed problems related to school operational inefficiency within the San Roque District, where discrepancies in financial management practices among school heads have been linked to varying levels of school performance. Issues such as misallocated resources, unutilized funding, and inadequate financial planning are prevalent and contribute to inefficiencies that hinder the educational outcomes. These

problems not only affect the immediate learning environment but also compromise the long-term sustainability of educational initiatives. By identifying and enhancing the role of corrective actions in financial stewardship, this study aims to provide actionable insights that could lead to more coherent and effective operational practices across schools in the district. Despite the extensive research on operational inefficiency in various global contexts, there remains a significant gap in understanding how corrective actions by school heads mediate the relationship between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency, particularly in the San Roque District of Davao City. Previous studies have predominantly focused on broader managerial practices and financial accountability, but few have delved into the specific role of corrective actions in enhancing financial stewardship and operational performance. This gap is critical, as understanding the mediating role of corrective actions could provide nuanced insights into how school leaders can effectively bridge the gap between financial management and operational outcomes, thereby fostering a more efficient educational environment. Moreover, the urgency to conduct this study in the San Roque District stems from the persistent issues of operational inefficiency observed in local public schools, such as misallocated resources, inadequate financial planning, and insufficient corrective measures. These problems not only impede the delivery of quality education but also compromise the long-term sustainability of educational initiatives in the district. By investigating the mediating role of corrective actions, this study aims to provide actionable recommendations that can help school heads enhance their financial stewardship skills and, consequently, improve the operational efficiency of their schools. Addressing this research gap is essential for developing targeted strategies that can mitigate inefficiencies and promote a more effective and responsive educational system in

San Roque District, ultimately benefiting both educators and students alike.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—This study is anchored on Stewardship Theory (Donaldson, 1990); Agency Theory (Jensen and Meckling, 1976); and Resource Dependency Theory (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978). Stewardship Theory posits that managers, motivated by altruism, are driven to act in the best interests of their organization. Proponents of this theory believe that stewards prioritize the organization's welfare over their personal gains, leading to decisions that benefit all stakeholders. This theory is particularly relevant to the study of financial stewardship skills of school heads and their impact on school operational efficiency. By framing school heads as stewards of their institutions, this theory supports the investigation into how their actions and decisions affect the broader educational environment. Specifically, it provides a theoretical basis for examining how corrective actions initiated by school heads as stewards can effectively mediate the relationship between their financial management practices and the operational success of schools, potentially leading to improved outcomes across educational settings. Also, Agency Theory examines the conflicts that arise between principals (owners) and agents (managers), particularly in terms of financial decisions and the oversight necessary to ensure agents act in the best interest of the principals. This theory often explores mechanisms to align the interests of both parties to mitigate agency problems.

In the context of this study, Agency Theory can be applied to understand the dynamics between school heads (agents) and educational stakeholders (principals) regarding financial management and operational efficiency. It offers a lens through which to view corrective actions as a form of internal control or mechanism that ensures school heads are effectively managing resources in line with stakeholder

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

expectations. Analyzing the relationship between financial stewardship skills and school efficiency through the lens of agency problems can highlight how corrective actions serve as a pivotal factor in aligning interests and enhancing school performance. Lastly, Resource Dependency Theory suggests that organizations are reliant on external resources and that their strategies are often shaped by the need to acquire and maintain these resources. The theory emphasizes the role of organizational leaders in managing dependencies and securing necessary resources to ensure organizational survival and

success. This theory is apt for exploring how school heads manage financial resources and dependencies to maintain or enhance school operational efficiency. It supports the study by providing a framework to examine how school heads' financial stewardship skills influence their ability to effectively manage resources, with corrective actions playing a mediating role. Investigating how these leaders navigate resource dependencies and implement corrective measures can shed light on strategies that enhance operational efficiency and educational quality, aligning resource management with institutional goals.

2. Methodology

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the research design, including details on the research respondents, ethical considerations, research instruments, and procedural steps. It also outlines the methods for data collection and analysis, ensuring a clear framework for the study.

2.1. Research Design—In the study, a quantitative approach, specifically utilizing descriptive-correlational methods and mediation analysis, was adopted to gather and analyze data pertinent to the study's objectives. A quantitative research approach involved the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena using statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It was primarily used to quantify the problem by generating numerical data or data that could be transformed into usable statistics (Ahmad et al., 2019). This approach was suitable for the study because it allowed for precise measurement of relationships between defined variables financial stewardship skills, corrective actions, and school operational efficiency. The quantitative method facilitated the objective analysis of data collected through surveys or existing records, enabling a robust assessment of the hypothesized mediation model. It also ensured replicability and provided a clear pathway for testing the significance and strength of the relationships among variables. The descriptive research method involved observing, describing, and documenting aspects of a situation as they naturally occurred. It included collecting quantitative data to explain what was observed but not necessarily why it occurred (Mohajan, 2020). Employing a descriptive research method was appropriate for this study because it helped in accurately capturing the current state of financial stewardship skills and operational efficiencies within schools. It allowed for a detailed description of the extent to which corrective actions were being implemented by school heads and the resultant effects on school operations. This method was integral in establishing a baseline understanding of the existing dynamics before examining the deeper causal relationships. The correlational research strategy was used to determine the relationship between two or more variables, understanding how they moved together without inferring a cause-and-effect link. This type of research indicated the strength and direction of a relationship between variables (Hassan, 2024). This strategy was apt for the study because it enabled the examination of the strength of association between financial stewardship skills, corrective actions, and operational efficiency. Correlational analysis allowed the researcher to identify patterns and predict potential outcomes based on observed relationships. It was crucial for the formulation of hypotheses regarding how these variables interacted and influenced each other in the educational context. Moreover, mediation analysis was a statistical approach used to understand how an independent variable influenced a dependent variable through a mediator variable. The Sobel z-Test was a method used in mediation analysis to test the significance of the mediation effect (Jérolon et al., 2021). Utilizing mediation analysis with the Sobel z-Test was highly relevant for this research as it sought to explore whether corrective actions mediated the relationship between the financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency. This analysis clarified the indirect effects of school heads' financial management on operational outcomes via corrective actions. It provided a rigorous statistical framework to validate the mediating role of corrective actions, offering insights into how improvements in one area (financial stewardship) could lead to enhancements in another (operational efficiency) through specific mecha-

nisms (corrective actions).

2.2. *Ethical Consideration*—The researcher strictly followed the established protocols outlined in the standard guidelines for executing the research, paying close attention to the specified criteria for managing both the population and the data. The survey questionnaires, along with other related materials, were submitted for evaluation and approval. Upon receiving the green light from the RMC-Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the subsequent phase of the study.

2.3. *Research Respondents*—The respondents of the study were the 260 teachers coming from San Roque District in Davao City. To come up with a sample of 260 teachers from a total population of 760 in San Roque District in Davao City using Slovin's formula, the researcher first calculated the sample size using the formula, where NNN is the population size and eee is the margin of error. For a population of 760 teachers and a margin of error of 0.05, the researcher computed nnn to be 260. For this study, the inclusion criteria for selecting respondents were specifically defined to gather the most relevant and insightful data. Respondents were required to be currently employed teachers within the public schools of San Roque District, having at least 5 years of teaching experience in the district to ensure familiarity with the school operations and financial practices under different school heads. Additionally, teachers must have been directly involved or have been involved in budgeting, resource allocation, or other financial management activities at their schools, providing them with firsthand exposure to the financial stewardship of school heads. This criterion was crucial for obtaining informed perspectives on the effectiveness and impact of the financial decisions and corrective actions taken by school leaders. Lastly, the respondents were required to participate voluntarily and provide consent to share their ex-

periences and observations while understanding the confidentiality and purpose of the study. Once the sample size had been established, the researcher employed random sampling methods to choose the respondents. Simple random sampling, a fundamental probability sampling technique, ensured that every individual in the population had an identical chance of being included in the sample. This approach guaranteed that all segments of the population had an equal likelihood of selection, effectively minimizing selection bias (Noor et al. 2022). For this particular study, the researcher assigned a unique number to each teacher within the population, then utilized a random number generator to select 260 teachers, thus maintaining an unbiased and representative sample of the overall population. Additionally, the researcher took careful measures to ensure that the selected teachers accurately represented the district's demographic and diverse characteristics, enhancing the study's overall validity.

2.4. *Research Instrument*—For the current study, the research methodology included the deployment of carefully structured survey questionnaires designed to explore the intricacies of the investigation. The questionnaire was divided into three distinct sections. The first part focused on the financial stewardship skills of school heads, examining this through a lens of four key indicators: budgeting accuracy, risk identification and mitigation, crisis management response, and compliance with financial policies. The Cronbach's alpha value for this instrument was 0.821, described as good and interpreted as reliable. Responses were collected using a 5-point Likert scale to assess the extent of agreement or disagreement with each statement, with subsequent analysis based on predefined ranges of means that categorized the data effectively. This structured approach ensured a comprehensive evaluation of the variables under study.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Financial stewardship skills are always observed among school heads.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Financial stewardship skills are oftentimes observed among school heads.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Financial stewardship skills are sometimes observed among school heads.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Financial stewardship skills are seldom observed among school heads.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Financial stewardship skills are never observed among school heads.

Note. This table shows the descriptive interpretation of financial stewardship skills based on the computed mean.

The second part of the instrument focused on the school operational efficiency of public schools. This questionnaire was designed to evaluate the domains namely teacher satisfaction and morale; teacher engagement in professional development; and collaboration and teamwork among teachers. The Cronbach’s alpha value for this instrument was 0.706, described as acceptable and interpreted as fairly reliable.

Responses were gathered using a 5-point Likert scale, allowing for precise measurement of agreement or disagreement with each item. This data was then analyzed using predefined mean ranges to effectively categorize and interpret the results. Such a methodical approach guaranteed a detailed and accurate assessment of the study’s key variables.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The process of data gathering for this study began with obtaining an official endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School at The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. This endorsement served as a formal recognition of the study’s academic value and alignment with the institution’s research objectives, ensuring institutional support for the research endeavor. Following this, the researcher secured ethical clearance from the Graduate School RMC-Research Ethics Committee (GSRMC-REC). The ethical clearance was crucial as it confirmed that the

study adhered to established ethical standards, particularly in terms of confidentiality, informed consent, and the welfare of the respondents. The ethical review process involved a comprehensive evaluation of the study’s methodology, data collection procedures, and the measures implemented to protect the rights and well-being of the respondents. This initial step not only legitimized the research but also ensured that it complied with ethical principles in educational research. After securing the endorsement from the Dean and obtaining ethical clearance, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Di-

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	School operational efficiency of public schools is always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	School operational efficiency of public schools is oftentimes evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	School operational efficiency of public schools is occasionally evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	School operational efficiency of public schools is rarely evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	School operational efficiency of public schools is never evident.

Note. This table describes the interpretation levels of school operational efficiency in public schools based on the computed mean range.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	Corrective actions of the school heads are always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	Corrective actions of the school heads are oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	Corrective actions of the school heads are sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	Corrective actions of the school heads are seldom observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	Corrective actions of the school heads are never observed.

Note. This table describes the level of observation for corrective actions of school heads based on the computed mean.

vision Superintendent of Davao City to conduct the study among the public secondary schools in San Roque District. This formal request included attaching copies of both the endorsement from the Graduate School and the ethical clearance certificate from the RMC-Research Ethics Committee. These attachments demonstrated that the research had undergone institutional and ethical scrutiny, reinforcing the legitimacy and credibility of the study. In the letter to the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher clearly outlined the purpose of the study, the scope of data collection, and the procedures

for maintaining respondent confidentiality and data security. Upon receiving approval from the Schools Division Superintendent, the researcher proceeded to coordinate with the school principals within San Roque District, providing them with clear information about the study's objectives and the roles of the teachers who would be participating. This systematic process ensured that all necessary permissions were obtained before the commencement of data collection, maintaining the integrity and ethical compliance of the research.

2.6. Data Analysis—The following statistical tools will be utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data:

Mean This statistical tool referred to the average score derived from the responses of teachers regarding their perceptions of financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency. It provided a central value that represented typical respondent views, allowing for an understanding of general attitudes toward financial management practices and their effects within schools. This measure enabled the researcher to identify overall trends and average perceptions, offering a clear view of the extent to which teachers recognized effective financial stewardship and operational efficiency in their respective schools.

Pearson Moment Product Correlation This statistical method was employed to measure the strength and direction of the linear relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency. It determined whether higher levels of financial competence among school heads were associated with greater operational efficiency in schools. A positive correlation indicated that as financial stewardship skills increased, so did school operational efficiency, while a negative correlation suggested an inverse relationship. This analysis was crucial for establishing the degree of

association between the variables under study.

Baron and Kenny's (1986) Method of Mediation. This method was applied to assess whether corrective actions significantly mediated the relationship between school heads' financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency. The process involved several regression analyses to test if corrective actions accounted for the influence of financial stewardship on operational efficiency. The analysis determined whether the direct effect of financial stewardship on operational efficiency decreased when the mediator (corrective actions) was included in the model. This method provided a structured approach to understanding the mediating role of corrective actions.

Sobel z-Test. This test was utilized to assess the significance of the mediation effect of corrective actions on the relationship between the financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency. It specifically determined if the indirect effect of the independent variable (financial stewardship skills) on the dependent variable (school operational efficiency) through the mediator (corrective actions) was statistically significant. This test provided a statistical basis for confirming the presence or absence of mediation within the study framework, enhancing the robustness of the mediation analysis results.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of financial stewardship skills of school heads, school operational efficiency, and corrective actions among public schools; the significant relationship among these variables; and the mediating effect of corrective actions on the relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency among public schools in San Roque District in Davao City.

3.1. Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads—The results on Table 1 reveal that the financial stewardship skills of school heads in San Roque District, Davao City, are generally rated as moderately extensive, with an overall mean of 3.29. This moderately extensive rating indicates that school heads sometimes demonstrate effective financial management practices across various domains, including budgeting accuracy, risk identification and mitigation, crisis management response, and compliance with financial policies. Such practices are essential for maintaining financial stability, accountability, and transparency within the school environment. This finding aligns with the perspective of Arroyo et al. (2024), who emphasized that strong financial stewardship is critical for the sustainable operation of educational institutions. The range of means among the four domains is from 3.16 to 3.40. Among the domains, crisis management response is the highest-rated, with a mean of 3.40, indicating that school heads are generally proficient in developing contingency plans and maintaining stability during financial crises. In contrast, budgeting accuracy is the lowest-rated domain, with a mean of 3.16, suggesting that school heads may encounter challenges in maintaining precise budget forecasting and adhering to budget limits. This finding is consistent with the observations of Dwangu and Mahlangu (2021), who noted that effective financial stewardship requires not only crisis management skills but also careful planning, continuous monitoring, and strict adherence to budgetary guidelines.

Table 1. Summary on Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads in San Roque District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Budgeting Accuracy	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Risk Identification and Mitigation	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Crisis Management Response	3.40	Extensive
Compliance with Financial Policies	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.29	Moderately Extensive

Note. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

3.2. *School Operational Efficiency*—Presented on Table 2 is the summary of school operational efficiency in San Roque District, Davao City, which is generally rated as extensive, with an overall mean of 3.45. This extensive rating indicates that schools in the district frequently demonstrate effective practices in maintaining teacher satisfaction and morale, promoting teacher engagement in professional development, and fostering collaboration and teamwork among teachers. Such practices are essential for creating a positive and supportive educational environment, which directly contributes to teacher motivation, instructional quality, and overall school effectiveness. This finding aligns with the perspective of Alm, Låftman, Sandahl, and Modin (2019), who emphasized that a strong school culture, continuous profes-

sional growth, and collaborative practices are critical components of effective school operations. Notably, the range of means among the three indicators is from 3.41 to 3.48. Among the indicators, teacher satisfaction and morale received the highest mean of 3.48, suggesting that schools prioritize creating a supportive work environment where teachers feel valued and motivated. In contrast, teacher engagement in professional development received the lowest mean of 3.41, indicating that while schools provide opportunities for professional growth, they may encounter challenges in ensuring consistent participation and access to high-quality training. This finding is consistent with the observations of Özgenel and Mert (2019), who noted that effective school operations require a balanced focus on teacher well-being, skill enhancement, and collaborative practices.

Table 2. Summary on School Operational Efficiency in San Roque District, Davao City

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Teacher Satisfaction and Morale	3.48	Extensive
Teacher Engagement in Professional Development	3.41	Extensive
Collaboration and Teamwork Among Teachers	3.45	Extensive
Overall	3.45	Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Evident; Extensive = Oftentimes Evident; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Evident; Less Extensive = Seldom Evident; Not Extensive = Never Evident.

3.3. *Corrective Actions of School Heads*—The results presented on Table 3 indicate that the corrective actions of school heads among public secondary schools in San Roque District, Davao City, are generally rated as moderately extensive, with an overall mean of 3.32. This

moderately extensive rating suggests that school heads sometimes demonstrate effective practices in implementing corrective actions to address financial discrepancies, enhance accountability, and ensure compliance with financial policies. Such practices are essential for main-

taining financial integrity and operational efficiency within the school. This observation aligns with the perspective of Håkansson and Adolfsson (2022), who emphasized that prompt and systematic corrective actions are critical for maintaining financial accountability and minimizing the impact of errors or non-compliance. The range of means among the eight statements is from 3.07 to 3.63. Among the statements, the highest-rated statement is Strengthening the financial training of staff as part of corrective actions rated as extensive with a mean of 3.63. In contrary, the lowest-rated statement is Improving resource allocation based on the outcomes of corrective actions rated as moderately extensive with a mean of 3.07. This finding is consistent with the observations of Van Ha and Murray (2021), who noted that while corrective actions are essential for maintaining compliance, their impact is maximized when they are directly linked to strategic resource management.

Table 3. Summary on Corrective Actions of School Heads Among Public Secondary Schools in San Roque District, Davao City

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1. Implementing corrective actions promptly when financial discrepancies are identified.	3.13	Moderately Extensive
2. Enhancing financial accountability through regular auditing and corrective measures.	3.18	Moderately Extensive
3. Improving resource allocation based on the outcomes of corrective actions.	3.07	Moderately Extensive
4. Addressing non-compliance with financial policies through immediate corrective actions.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
5. Regularly updating staff on changes made as a result of corrective actions.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
6. Encouraging transparency in financial decisions following corrective interventions.	3.55	Extensive
7. Strengthening the financial training of staff as part of corrective actions.	3.63	Extensive
8. Systematically monitoring the impact of corrective actions on school operations.	3.37	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.32	Moderately Extensive

Legend. Very Extensive = Always Observed; Extensive = Oftentimes Observed; Moderately Extensive = Sometimes Observed; Less Extensive = Seldom Observed; Not Extensive = Never Observed.

3.4. *Relationship Among Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads, School Operational Efficiency, and Corrective Actions* —

The results on the analysis on the relationship among financial stewardship skills of school heads, school operational efficiency, and corrective actions among public schools in San Roque District in Davao City are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned. The results in Table 4 reveal a significant positive relationship between the financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency among public schools in San Roque District, Davao City, with an r-value of 0.602 and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This finding indicates that as school heads demonstrate stronger financial stewardship skills, including budgeting, risk management, crisis response, and compliance, the overall operational efficiency of schools tends to improve. Such efficiency is reflected in enhanced teacher satisfaction, professional development, and collaborative practices within the school. This aligns with the perspective of Keykha et al. (2022), who emphasized that effective financial management is a critical component of school leadership, as it ensures that financial resources are effectively allocated to support educational goals. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency is therefore rejected. The analysis further shows a strong positive relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and their implementation of cor-

rective actions, with an r-value of 0.770 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance. This result suggests that school heads who are proficient in financial stewardship are more likely to identify, address, and rectify financial discrepancies through effective corrective actions. This finding is consistent with the observations of Mungai (2024), who highlighted that strong financial stewardship skills are directly linked to the ability to implement corrective measures that enhance financial accountability and transparency. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between financial stewardship skills and corrective actions is thus rejected. Moreover, a moderate positive relationship is identified between school operational efficiency and corrective actions among public schools in San Roque District, Davao City, with an r-value of 0.470 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates that schools that maintain operational efficiency are more likely to consistently implement corrective actions to address financial or procedural issues. Such a relationship suggests that efficient school operations, characterized by high teacher morale, professional development, and collaboration, are reinforced by the systematic use of corrective actions to maintain accountability and quality. This observation aligns with the view of Devanadera and Ching (2023), who emphasized that operational efficiency in schools is not only a product of effective leadership but also of continuous monitoring and corrective measures that sustain high-performance standards. The null hypothesis of no significant relationship between school operational efficiency and corrective actions is therefore rejected.

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3.5. —Mediating Effect of Corrective Actions on the Relationship Between Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads and School Operational Efficiency

The results on the anal-

ysis on the mediating effect of corrective actions on the relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency among public schools in

Table 4. Relationship Among Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads, School Operational Efficiency, and Corrective Actions in San Roque District, Davao City

Variables	School Operational Efficiency	Corrective Actions
Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads	0.602**	0.770**
	0.000	0.000
School Operational Efficiency	1	0.470**
		0.000

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.00 < r < 0.3$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$.

San Roque District in Davao City is shown in Table 5. The path coefficients presented in Table 5 reveal the direct and indirect relationships between financial stewardship skills (FSS) of school heads, corrective actions (CA), and school operational efficiency (SOE) in San Roque District, Davao City. In Step 1, the path from corrective actions to school operational efficiency (CA → SOE) is not statistically significant, with an estimate of 0.018, a z-value of 0.220, and a p-value of 0.826. This result indicates that corrective actions alone do not directly influence school operational efficiency. In contrast, Step 2 shows that financial stewardship skills have a significant direct effect on school operational efficiency (FSS → SOE), with an estimate of 0.605, a z-value of 7.588, and a p-value of <0.001. Step 3 demonstrates that financial stewardship skills significantly influence corrective actions (FSS → CA), with

an estimate of 0.758, a z-value of 19.448, and a p-value of <0.001. These results suggest that while financial stewardship skills are directly linked to both corrective actions and operational efficiency, corrective actions do not independently enhance operational outcomes. The parameter estimates provide a detailed breakdown of the direct, indirect, and total effects of financial stewardship skills on school operational efficiency. The direct effect of financial stewardship skills on operational efficiency (FSS → SOE) is significant, with an estimate of 0.605 ($p < 0.001$). The indirect effect, which measures the pathway through corrective actions (FSS → CA → SOE), is 0.013, with a z-value of 0.220 and a p-value of 0.826, indicating that this indirect effect is not statistically significant. The total effect, combining both the direct and indirect pathways, is 0.618 ($p < 0.001$).

Table 5. Mediating Effect of Corrective Actions on the Relationship Between Financial Stewardship Skills of School Heads and School Operational Efficiency in San Roque District, Davao City

Path Coefficients				
Steps	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
(Step 1) CA → SOE	0.018	0.081	0.220	0.826
(Step 2) FSS → SOE	0.605	0.080	7.588	<.001
(Step 3) FSS → CA	0.758	0.039	19.448	<.001

Step 4 (Parameter Estimates)				
Effect Type	Parameter Estimates	Estimate	Std. Error	p-value
Indirect Effect Components	FSS → CA → SOE	0.013	0.061	0.826
Direct Effect	FSS → SOE	0.605	0.080	<.001
Total Effect	FSS → SOE	0.618	0.051	<.001

Additional Information:

Ratio Index = 0.02103

Sobel z-Test value = 0.2222, $p = 0.82415$

Legend: FSS = Financial Stewardship Skills; SOE = School Operational Efficiency; CA = Corrective Actions

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the mediating effect of corrective actions on the relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency among public schools utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected the 260 public elementary school teachers within San Roque District in Davao City as the respondents through simple random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. The results of the study are summarize as follows: The findings of this study reveal that the financial stewardship skills of school heads in San Roque District, Davao City, are generally rated as moderately extensive. This rating suggests that school heads demonstrate effective practices in financial management, including budgeting accuracy, risk identification and mitigation, crisis management response, and compliance with financial policies. Among these domains, crisis management response is the most evident, indicating that school heads are particularly skilled in managing financial crises. In contrast, budgeting accuracy is the least evident, suggesting that school heads may encounter challenges in maintaining precise budget forecasting and adherence. These findings emphasize the importance of enhancing financial planning skills among school leaders to ensure more accurate and reliable budget management. In terms of school operational efficiency, the results indicate that public secondary schools in San Roque District generally demonstrate extensive operational efficiency. Teacher satisfaction and morale are the most evident, reflecting strong support for teacher well-being and motivation within schools. This suggests that schools in the district are successful in creating positive work environments that foster teacher engagement and commitment. However, teacher engagement in professional development is the least evident, indicating that schools may face challenges in providing consistent access to high-quality training opportunities. Such findings highlight the need for schools to enhance their professional development programs to maintain teacher competence and instructional effectiveness. The analysis of corrective actions among school heads in San Roque District reveals a generally moderate level of implementation. Among the specific corrective actions, strengthening the financial training of staff is the most evident, suggesting that school heads prioritize capacity-building as a key corrective measure. Conversely, improving resource allocation based on the outcomes of corrective actions is the least evident, indicating that school heads may struggle to use the results of corrective actions to optimize resource distribution. These findings underscore the importance of not only implementing corrective actions but also ensuring that their outcomes are systematically applied to improve school resource management. The results further reveal significant relationships between financial stewardship skills of school heads, school operational efficiency, and corrective actions. Specifically, there is a strong positive relationship between financial stewardship skills and corrective actions, indicating that school heads who demonstrate strong financial stewardship are more likely to implement effective

tive corrective measures. Additionally, a moderate positive relationship exists between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency, suggesting that effective financial management directly enhances overall school operations. Moreover, a moderate positive relationship is identified between school operational efficiency and corrective actions, which implies that schools that maintain efficient operations are also more consistent in implementing corrective measures. Finally, the analysis of the mediating effect of corrective actions on the relationship between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency reveals that corrective actions do not significantly mediate this relationship. The indirect effect of financial stewardship skills on school operational efficiency through corrective actions is not statistically significant. Instead, the direct effect of financial stewardship skills on operational efficiency is substantial, indicating that school heads' financial stewardship skills directly enhance school operations without the need for corrective actions as a mediating factor. These findings suggest that while corrective actions are important, the direct impact of financial stewardship on operational efficiency is more pronounced.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study several conclusions were generated: The findings of this study conclude that the financial stewardship skills of school heads in San Roque District, Davao City, are generally rated as moderately extensive. This suggests that while school heads demonstrate effective practices in financial management, there is room for improvement, particularly in budgeting accuracy, which is the least evident domain. This implies that school heads should enhance their skills in budget forecasting, monitoring, and compliance to ensure that financial resources are effectively managed. Schools are encouraged to provide targeted training on advanced budgeting techniques and financial planning strategies

to strengthen the financial stewardship skills of school leaders. The study also concludes that school operational efficiency in San Roque District is generally extensive, reflecting positive outcomes in teacher satisfaction, professional development, and collaboration. However, teacher engagement in professional development is the least evident, indicating that schools may encounter challenges in consistently providing high-quality training opportunities. This implies that schools should strengthen their professional development programs by offering diverse training options, promoting active teacher participation, and ensuring access to external learning opportunities. Schools may also consider adopting a needs-based approach to professional development, tailoring training sessions to match teachers' specific skill gaps and interests. The findings further conclude that corrective actions among school heads in San Roque District are generally moderately extensive, suggesting that while corrective measures are implemented, their effectiveness may be limited. Notably, improving resource allocation based on the outcomes of corrective actions is the least evident, implying that school heads may struggle to apply the results of corrective measures to optimize resource management. This implies that school heads should not only focus on identifying and addressing issues but also on using corrective outcomes as a basis for strategic resource planning. Schools may consider providing training on data-driven decision-making and resource optimization to enhance the impact of corrective actions. Additionally, the study confirms that there are significant relationships among financial stewardship skills of school heads, school operational efficiency, and corrective actions. Strong financial stewardship skills are directly linked to effective corrective actions and improved operational efficiency, highlighting the importance of strong financial management in maintaining effective school operations. This implies that schools should prior-

itize the development of financial management skills among their leaders to ensure both proactive corrective measures and overall operational efficiency. Regular monitoring and evaluation of financial stewardship practices can further enhance accountability and transparency. Finally, the analysis of the mediating effect of corrective actions reveals that corrective actions do not significantly mediate the relationship between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency. Instead, the direct effect of financial stewardship skills on operational efficiency is more pronounced. This finding supports the Stewardship Theory (Donaldson, 1990), which emphasizes the importance of leadership responsibility and accountability in achieving organizational success. However, it partially contradicts Agency Theory (Jensen Meckling, 1976), which suggests that corrective measures are necessary to align management actions with organizational goals. The result also supports Resource Dependency Theory (Pfeffer and Salancik, 1978), which highlights the importance of effective resource management in maintaining organizational stability. These findings imply that school heads with strong financial stewardship skills can directly enhance school operational efficiency, even without relying heavily on corrective measures.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are offered to inform policy, school leadership, teaching practice, and future research: To enhance the financial stewardship skills of school heads in San Roque District, Davao City, it is recommended that schools prioritize improving budgeting accuracy, as this domain demonstrated the lowest mean among the aspects of financial stewardship. School heads should be provided with targeted training on advanced budgeting techniques, financial forecasting, and effective budget monitoring. Additionally, schools may establish regular budget review sessions and mentorship programs, al-

lowing school heads to learn from experienced financial managers. Such initiatives can help school heads develop a more precise and systematic approach to budget planning, ensuring that financial resources are efficiently managed. In terms of school operational efficiency, schools should focus on increasing teacher engagement in professional development, which has the lowest mean among the domains of operational efficiency. To address this, schools can diversify their professional development programs, offering a wide range of training options that cater to teachers' specific needs and interests. Promoting active participation through incentives, recognizing teachers' efforts in skill enhancement, and ensuring access to external training opportunities can further encourage continuous professional growth. By fostering a culture of continuous learning, schools can ensure that teachers remain motivated and equipped with the latest pedagogical skills. Regarding corrective actions, school heads are encouraged to enhance their ability to improve resource allocation based on the outcomes of corrective actions, which was identified as the least evident practice. Schools may conduct workshops on data-driven decision-making and resource optimization, providing school heads with practical strategies to align resource management with corrective outcomes. Furthermore, establishing a clear process for evaluating the results of corrective actions and using these insights to inform resource allocation can enhance the overall effectiveness of corrective measures. This approach can help schools maximize the impact of corrective actions on resource management and operational efficiency. To further strengthen the relationship between financial stewardship skills of school heads and school operational efficiency, it is recommended that school heads refine their corrective action strategies. Since corrective actions demonstrated the weakest positive relationship with school operational efficiency, schools should provide train-

ing on effective corrective measures, including root cause analysis, continuous improvement methods, and systematic follow-up. Regular monitoring of corrective outcomes can also help ensure that corrective actions are effectively applied, leading to more consistent improvements in school operations. Such an approach can ensure that corrective actions are not merely reactive but are integrated into a proactive system of continuous improvement. Finally, given that corrective actions do not significantly mediate the relationship between financial stewardship skills and school operational efficiency, it is recommended that schools focus directly on strengthening school heads' financial stewardship skills. Schools can achieve this by offering targeted training on financial planning, risk management, crisis response, and compliance management. Moreover, promoting a culture of proactive financial management, where school heads are encouraged to anticipate and prevent financial issues rather than relying solely on corrective measures, can further enhance school operational efficiency. By fostering strong financial stewardship, schools can ensure that their leaders are well-prepared to maintain financial stability and operational excellence.

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